

Windbreak Autonomous Fabricator (WAF).

1. Introduction: The Threat of Martian Regolith and the Need for Active Protection

For long-term missions to Mars, a problem arises: the planetary environment is actively hostile to technology. The threat comes not from the wind itself, but from its constant companion — micronized, electrostatically charged, abrasive regolith.

Three destruction mechanisms:

1. Abrasive wear: Regolith particles have sharp, unrounded edges. A flow of such abrasive at speeds of even 20-30 m/s acts like sandblasting, gradually destroying external coatings, optics, seals, and unprotected mechanical components.
2. Thermal crisis: Settling on radiation panels, dust sharply reduces their heat dissipation efficiency, which can lead to overheating and failure of critical systems, especially energy systems (nuclear reactors) and habitat modules.
3. Energy starvation: A layer of dust just 0.1 mm thick on solar panels reduces their output by 40% or more. After a global dust storm, the panels may be completely disabled, as happened with the InSight mission.

Existing passive protection methods include burial and placement behind natural terrain folds. As a proposal, the construction of artificial wind-dampening and dust-trapping screens is suggested.

2. WAF: Principle

WAF is a mobile factory with a closed cycle, whose operation consists of maximum utilization of exclusively local resources (ISRU) and complete rejection of delivering any construction materials from Earth.

The WAF concept proposes the idea of "territory engineering before crew arrival" — automatic devices pre-prepare the territory, making it safe for deploying complex and vulnerable infrastructure.

3. Detailed Description of Architecture and Technological Modules

3.1. Power Platform and Complex Life Support

Chassis: Specialized tracked chassis. Each track is an independent electric module with a sealed drive. Wide tracks with perforations reduce soil adhesion. The chassis frame serves as a power frame for mounting heavy modules and damping systems for press operation.

Power Plant: Compact fast neutron nuclear reactor of the "Kilopower/DUFF" type.

Electrical Part: Powers the chassis electric drives, pumps, fans, onboard AI-computer, communications, and sensors.

Thermal Part: Heat carrier with a temperature of ~ 800 °C enters a two-circuit system.

First circuit (high-temperature): directly from the reactor.

Second circuit (working): through a heat exchanger transfers heat to a thermal accumulator and then to the press-form heating elements.

Hermetic Module: The entire production cycle is enclosed in a housing with multi-layer vacuum insulation (MLI) and an internal climate system. This is a "clean zone" protected from external dust, radiation, and cold.

3.2. Technological Chain

Module 1: Intelligent Intake and Separation

Design: Combined rotary-screw intake with vibrating screen. The outer drum with pockets captures soil, the inner screw advances it through a sieve with 5 mm mesh.

Separation: Fraction >5 mm (pebbles, stones) is dumped down through a cut-off valve. The fine-dispersed fraction (<5 mm), comprising $\sim 85\%$ of the regolith, is then fed to the receiving hopper.

Module 2: Dosing and Mixture Preparation.

Regolith from the hopper enters the mixing chamber, where a doser introduces the binding modifier.

Modifier Variants:

Optimal (sulfur): Extracted from sulfate deposits. Addition 3-5% by mass. Melts at $\sim 115^{\circ}\text{C}$, creating a strong matrix upon hardening. Sulfur is a nice bonus, but not the basis of the system. If it is found in sufficient quantity — excellent, we get noticeably stronger and faster-hardening material. If not — the machine simply continues to operate in baseline mode.

Alternative (calcium perchlorate): Present in regolith. Can act as a flux during heating, reducing the sintering temperature.

If none of this is available, proceed without them.

Module 3: Hot Forming Press-Autoclave (Hot Pressing Chamber).

This is the heart of WAF. It is a closed chamber with active heating of walls and punch.

Cycle Process:

1. Loading: The mixture from the mixer is fed into the open press-form with an insert defining the "superellipse" cross-section (Lamé curve).
2. Closing and Pressing: The punch descends, creating preliminary pressure for compaction.
3. Heating and Final Pressing: Heating of the form walls to 450-500°C is activated (heat from the reactor). Sulfur melts, wetting the regolith particles. Simultaneously, pressure increases to 15-20 MPa. Under these conditions, liquid-phase sintering occurs — regolith particles do not melt but are bound by the sulfur matrix.
4. Cooling and Pressure Release: Cooling and pressure release: Heating is turned off. The punch rises, pulling the hot pillar with it. The pillar is ejected from the hot form onto a cooling table, where it releases heat through a radiation circuit. The press-form itself, remaining hot, is immediately ready for a new portion of cold mixture. This allows separating the form heating cycle and product cooling cycle, maintaining high work pace.
5. Ejection: The punch rises, the lower pusher outputs the finished pillar to the receiving table.

Everything looks as follows: regolith is dumped into the chamber (4), from where after the doors (3) open it passes through special chutes (2) and enters the press form (5), where after filling it will be compressed under pressure by the punch (1). The walls (6) can be used not only to hold the shape but also to transfer the heat necessary for sintering.

In the end, we should get a pillar with a superellipse shape.

Module 4: Installation and Fixation System.

Combined manipulator-immersion device.

Boom manipulator (6 degrees of freedom) with a grip repeating the pillar shape, takes the product from the table.

A rotary-impact drill is mounted on the same unit.

Installation Algorithm:

- The manipulator drills a pilot hole 0.5-0.7 m deep.
- A portion of the same binder (sulfur) is injected into the bottom of the hole by a doser.
- The manipulator installs the pillar in the hole and applies axial force (vibro-compaction), burying it to the calculated depth.
- The binder at the bottom, heated from the pillar heat or from a separate mini-heater, fixes the base.

4. Aerodynamic Rationale for the Shape and Efficiency

Pillars with a "superellipse" cross-section (equation $|x/a|^n + |y/b|^n = 1$) are chosen not by chance.

At exponent $n = 2.5 - 3.5$, the body is streamlined smoothly, without forming rigid vortices characteristic of a cylinder.

Effect: Wind, flowing around such a shape, destabilizes and loses energy on flow separation along the entire length of the pillar, rather than concentrating at one point. This turns a solid wall of pillars into an effective wind speed dampener in the surface layer.

Placement: Optimal "forest" geometry — checkerboard order.

In the end, we should get Mars covered with pillars to dampen wind force.

Additions

Final characteristics (pillar size, productivity, machine mass) will be derived from the primary mission requirements.

